
Organizational Wellbeing Practices and Employee Work Behavior in Selected Manufacturing Company, Lagos, Nigeria

ADEGUN, *kehinde Caleb*¹, Akinbo T. M. (PhD)²

¹Lead City University, Ibadan

²Department of Management & Accounting Lead City University, Ibadan

ABSTRACT

As organizational performance and success rely on the employees, there is an issue of how organization actions can best take care of their employees and ensure their well-being. This study examines the effect of organizational well-being practices on employee work behaviour in Danade manufacturing company, Lagos. In this study, survey research design was considered suitable for gathering data on organizational wellbeing and employee work behavior in the manufacturing company. The study had a population size of 200 from which sample size of 80 was realized via formula at 5% error tolerance and 95% confidence level. Instrument utilized for data acquisition was principally questionnaire and interview. The sources of data were collected from primary data, the primary data was collected by a validated semi-structured questionnaire, analyzed using survey method analysis; and summarized using descriptive statistics to establish the mean count of organizational wellbeing practices and their behaviour. The result of the study shows ($r = 0.046$, $p < 0.05$) to have a significant positive relationship between organizational well-being and job performance as also shows ($\beta = 0.21$, $p < 0.05$) that wellbeing practices for job satisfaction such as work life balance, employee development and empowerment are significant predictors of job satisfaction and other work behaviour. The study concludes that organizational wellbeing is a factor in influencing job behaviour in manufacturing companies. The study recommended that manufacturing companies should implement wellbeing practices that will stimulate employee engagement and behaviour, job satisfaction and productivity.

KEYWORDS: Organization Wellbeing Practices, Employee Behaviour, Job Satisfaction, Job Performance

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
13 June 2025

Available on:
<https://ijrsr.org/>

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Employee well-being has turned out to be a dire concern for organizations in recent years. There is an increasing demand of job and there is much pressure to perform the jobs, it is known that employees are experiencing high levels of stress and anxiety, of which can have negative consequences for both employees and organizations, as well as decreased job performance, turnover and absenteeism. Some of the main contributing factors to organizational performance is by embracing the well-being of employees so as to ensure that organization attracts and retains the top talents, which expressively influence productivity (Krekel, Ward and De Neve, 2019). Employee well-being has been known to be an interesting topic, as human resource is the most vital resource in productivity in organization. Employee well-being has been recognized to have a direct connection with an organization's productivity, as has been observed in conditions where employee absence and lack of commitment due to mental health conditions such as stress have negatively affected their companies (Holbeche, 2009). The safety problems such as accidental injuries and absenteeism due to mental health issues notably have high costs on an organization. Thereby, the organizations have put in place measures that considers employees' well-being and safety to prevent such costs (Bach and Edwards, 2013)

Numerous studies have acknowledged that healthy employees with high satisfaction derived in increased efficiency, productivity and profitability for organizations that has implemented supportive policies. It is confirmed by Armstrong (2016) that when organizations yield to a proactive approach to support employee well-being through good employment practices, flexible return to work policies and other rehabilitation strategies, such organizations are expected to have employees that spend most of their time at the workplace and successfully contribute to productivity. According to the International Labor Organization (2022), employee

Organizational Wellbeing Practices and Employee Work Behavior in Selected Manufacturing Company, Lagos, Nigeria

well-being which is also known as workplace well-being, refers to all the aspects of working life quality and physical environment, workers' feelings about their work, the nature of the work environment and work organization. Bakker et al. (2019) established an evidence that employees' health and general well-being regarding work are some of the most crucial factors that significantly influence the organization's performance. This denotes that taking care of such employees' well-being is relative to the organization's likely performance. Shin and Konrad (2017) further emphasized that the productivity and performance of an organization depend on the employees. Therefore, it suggests that if the employees are in good mental, emotional and physical health, it increases the likelihood of high productivity and performance in such an organization.

The research is focused on employee well-being. It is when workers are happy, both at home and in the office that productivity rises. One of a company's most valuable resources is its employees. Placing money into employees' education and health is a good way to boost the firm's bottom line. The major goal of every company that invests in its employees' health and happiness is to attract, retain, and motivate the best possible workforce. Organizations should prioritize more of employee well-being in order to increase employee happiness, which in turn increases the likelihood that workers will remain with the firm. The happiness of workers is crucial to the success of any business. It is necessary to keep staff happy and boost productivity, businesses should invest in employee well-being programs. It's often assumed that competent employees also provide quality results. The health of both workers and their productivity in the workplace are strongly influenced by their level of well-being. When workers are satisfied with the benefits they acquire from their employer, they won't have any need to go elsewhere for fulfilment (Shih, 2020). The success of an organization depends on the productivity and happiness of its workers. Organizations of all magnitudes and types are increasingly concerned with the effects of employee happiness on productivity on the job. Employees' productivity may be improved in various ways related to their overall sense of well-being. In order for workers to be happy in their jobs and contribute to the firm's success, management need to ensure they have contact to resources that will promote their mental, physical, social, professional, and societal health.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

As organizational performance and success rely on the employees and their well-being, there is an issue of how organization actions can best take care of their employees and ensure their well-being to give assurance of good organizational performance and greater success. It is therefore obvious that employees' actions and behavior's significantly influence the outcomes and productivity of the organization. Quite a few researches have been conducted on the relationship between the employee-wellbeing and how it impacts organizational performance, yet, there still occurs a research gap in the mental well-being of employees in the current job performance research. In spite of the several research, significant changes occur with time, economic, social and psychological issues that impact the employees. There are also constant changes in the workplace, employee anticipations and resource-related human problems that are not captured in the past research. These concerns and changes present a gap in the available literature which may not be able to provide solutions to the recent issues at the workplace to address the various causes that influence employees' well-being at the recent times. Without recent research that apprehends the evolving issues on human resource management and employees' anticipations and wellbeing, it turn out to be challenging to comprehend how organizations can optimize their employees to get a greater performance.

Thus, this study focuses on providing information on employees' well-being while considering the recent and emerging issues influencing them at the workplace and in life and examining how it impacts their impact and performance at the workplace. Regardless of the effort of managers in certifying that there is a high performance, the manufacturing industry has pressure because of global market competition, high internal standards in which the human resource has been pulling to meet these demands. This has caused low production of finished goods in Nigeria. The common organization is demanding to lessen costs through retrenching amongst other cost reduction strategies. Further emergent problems include frequent strikes in manufacturing companies. The employees criticized for poor working condition, poor payments, poor machines, obsolete technology, poor welfare policies, and poor employee growth.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aims to investigate how employees' well-being impacts employee's performance

1. To examine the relationship between employee well-being and job performance in a manufacturing company in Lagos.
2. To identify the magnitudes of employee well-being that are strongly associated to job satisfaction in a manufacturing company.
3. To examine the moderating effect of demographic factors on the relationship between employee well-being and job performance in a manufacturing company.

Statement of Hypotheses

Based on the objectives, the following hypotheses were formulated to guide this study;

HO1: There is no significant relationship between employee wellbeing and job performance

HO2: There is no significant relationship between employee wellbeing and job satisfaction

HO3: There is no significant relationship between employee wellbeing and organizational commitment

Significance of the Study

This study is necessary in line for its vital contributions to literature and industries managers. The study contributes to knowledge by providing a recent information as regards employees' well-being and how it can have greater on impacts organizational performance in the present business environment. It therefore becomes a vital source of knowledge and information that several scholars can use as references to conduct progressive research on the area in its comprehensions into what impacts the employees' well-being in the current times and the imperative impacts on organizational performance. The perceptions from the study are hence useful to employers and human resource managers by instituting the prospects of the employees on the use of initiatives aimed at stimulating their well-being at the workplace and how employees can easily be motivated to enhance their performance and productivity at their workplace.

Scope of the Study

This study explores the effects of employee well-being on the performance of employees in manufacturing industry in Lagos. As regards employee well-being, the study covers employees' mental, psychological, emotional and physical health as influenced by the organizational culture. The study hence investigates how employee well-being influences productivity in an organization.

Research Questions

1. How can employee well-being resourcefulness impact the general performance of an organization as regards to productivity in various industries?
2. What is the importance of employee well-being at the workplace in association with an organization's strategy and performance?
3. How will demographic factors (age, gender, tenure) influence the relationship between employee well-being and job performance in a manufacturing company?

Limitation of the Study

The major limitation of the study was the busy schedule of the human resource managers and the employees, which made it challenging to collect facts from the respondents physically. Nevertheless, a virtual investigation helped to solve the problem.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance of employee gives a standard of measuring the ability of employee behavior as used in performance criteria. Employees are normally rated with quantity, quality, or even competence of doing work against some certain set standards. Performance of employees may be attained through the use of appraisal systems which comprises the use of performance review, graphic rating scale, and balanced scorecards, (Saffar & Obeidat, 2020).

Globally, employee retention is a crucial aspect of personnel management, hence the employee performance in the current study using production quantity, job satisfaction, efficiency in service, and quality of service as indicators in measuring the performance of the employee. The indicators can then be measured against the reward system, welfare, and policies, organization culture, and technology correspondingly.

Theoretical Framework

Employee Well-being

Employee well-being denotes the whole quality of an employee's experience at work which comprises of physical, emotional, and psychological well-being. Employee well-being can also be measured using several magnitudes, including job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and psychological well-being. Employee well-being entails a satisfied living and working condition. Employees are one of the most significant assets of the organization. The worth of employee's assets can be increased by devoting in the training and well-being activities of employees in the organization. The core reason behind providing the well-being of employee in the organization is for efficiency, healthy and satisfied labor force for the organization. Employee well-being measure can be achieved by the organization to gratify their employees and increase the level of productivity in the organization.

Several factors such as the tools and resources that the employees have access to, the relationships they have with their superior and colleagues, workplace safety, salaries, wages, bonuses and the hours worked hence significantly influence the well-being of employees in any organization (Pilbeam, 2011). According to Bach and Edwards (2013), employee well-being is vital to an establishment's healthy working environment, which turns to greater results for the employee and overall performance improvement. Hence, organizations that endeavor to promote the well-being of their employees will stand a better chance of succeeding (Armstrong, 2016). The employer should identify and control the stress levels among the employees in order to create a positive and productive environment that attracts them to commit themselves and outperform their expectations.

Organizational Wellbeing Practices and Employee Work Behavior in Selected Manufacturing Company, Lagos, Nigeria

Numerous studies have shown the monetary significance of wellness programs in the workplace in terms of health care and productivity. Nevertheless, a number of scholars claimed that employees should also factor in non-monetary factors, such as the health and happiness of their workplace. These outcomes may be used as indicators of worker wellness, workplace safety, and morale. This study explores into the best practices for creating a health outline of employee well-being. The corporate well-being profile is a device for communicating vital health outcomes to business executives interconnected to the working setting (Altomonte et al., 2020). In this study, a look at the facts to examine whether to improve employees' happiness leads to greater output and also yields to financial gains for companies. Employee well-being has been established to have a significant positive association with performance, higher levels of happiness at work are associated to greater output.

The study looks into current state of employee wellbeing in manufacturing industries, improving employees' mental health so as to derive benefits for both the firm and the employees. When it comes to young employees, mental well-being is connected with physical health, emotional satisfaction, and increased happiness, making it an important component of overall well-being. Employee well-being can be assumed in the perspective of stress and resource management. Organizations basically must know how to build a happy and productive workforce in order to benefit from the joyful employees and dynamic workforce impression. Organizations that compromise on employee safety will definitely have an impending greater number of industrial accidents and misfortune of which will leads to an increase in compensation cost. It is noted that occupational accidents due to safety slackness can also destabilize employees and weaken their productivity, performance and motivation.

Empirical Review

The Happy-Productive Worker Hypothesis

The hypothesis states that a joyful and happy employee will have a tendency to be more productive, suggesting that an employee's performance is as a result of the well-being of such an employee (Christensen, 2017). However, Pajic (2022) states that the well-being and productivity of a worker are bogus and mainly be influenced by the personality attribute of an individual like as self-worth. It hence tests the hypothesis that a happy employee is expected to be more productive and accomplish better than others. The concept is suitable for this study because it supports the characteristic for employers to take care of the employees' well-being and maintain a happy workforce that is expected to be more dedicated to their work so as to achieve the organizational objectives.

Broaden-and-build theory

The theory was anticipated and brought to existence by Wright, Cropanzano and Bonett (2007). The theory states that job satisfaction measures employee well-being and performance. The theory justified that employees with greater levels of psychological well-being would have a robust relationship with performance. The theory highlights that if an employee have a positive thoughts, it boosts their momentary thought of action which develop to create more of innovative and creativity, which thus enabling them to come up with alternatives for solving a particular situation (Zhao, Li, Zheng and Zhang, 2022). This theory accordingly clarifies the employers providing an atmosphere that keeps employees in a positive mood, the employees are expected to reduce emotional stress thereby increasing their approach to their work which directly influences their productivity to enhance the organization's performance.

Healthy Workplace and Well-Being Programmes

Healthy workplace practices take many forms including those directed at the physical work environment (safety, ergonomics); health practices (supporting healthy lifestyles, fitness, diet); and social environmental and personal resources (organizational culture, a sense of control over one's work, work-family balance). Various healthy workplace researchers have turn out to be convinced that organizations must also become more accustomed to the harmful consequences of workplace stress and other psycho-social factors (Lowe's, 2003). In view of this, it was made cleared that several employees link psycho-social factors including interpersonal relationships, ` healthy relations with supervisors and the availability of other forms in support of opinion of how healthy a workplace should be. In this esteem, business leaders are also increasingly conscious of the importance of reducing stress in the workplace. Possible remedies to poor workplace health include vacation benefits, flexible time, work-life balance, effective and open communications, job enrichment etc. (Lowe's, 2003).

Employee Performance

Employees are assessed on how well they do their job compared with a set of standards to be determined by the employer. Employees' performance in organizations should be monitored and evaluated in order to ensure the level of performance is not decreasing in the organization.

Performance measures such as performance appraisal systems which uses balance score cards, graphic rating scale and performance reviews can be used by the organization to institute the cause for a drop in performance, hence the Human Resource Manager can know what the problem is from the feedback received from performance indicators (Drake International, 2012).

Performance indicators give the Human Resource department room to talk over with the employees about their performance which in return, the employees can be able to give their feedback.

Organizational Wellbeing Practices and Employee Work Behavior in Selected Manufacturing Company, Lagos, Nigeria

Research Methodology

In this study, survey research design was considered suitable for gathering data on employee wellbeing and employee performance, this assists in describing existing conditions of employee's wellbeing and performance in Danade manufacturing company, Lagos. This method was used to determine the employee insights, attitudes, performance and values towards the working environment and conditions.

Population of Study

The population of concern consisted of both the skilled and unskilled labours, technicians, engineers, electricians in Danade manufacturing company, Lagos. A population of 200 staff formed the population of study. 95 questionnaires were distributed and 80 were answered and returned, 15 were not returned.

Sampling Strategy

The study used a stratified random sampling technique to select participants of staff from various departments in the manufacturing industry.

Research Design

The study used a quantitative research approach, the data were collected from a sample of employees using a self-report questionnaire in the manufacturing industry.

Data Collection

The method of data collection used for the study was from both the primary source and secondary source of data using questionnaire and company data. The primary data was collected using questionnaire and was summarized using descriptive statistics to establish the mean count with statements on employee wellbeing and performance.

Data Analysis

As the response data were received, the data were analyzed. The primary data was collected by a self-administered structured questionnaire and was analyzed using a survey method analysis and summarized using descriptive statistics to establish the mean count of employee wellbeing and performance. Further analysis was done to categorize the data based on the survey questions. It provided a means to determine the major categories for discussion in this study. The study also applied regression analysis of the dependent and independent variables. The use of computer software using SPSS was analyzed for data analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

The method of analysis used in the study was a survey method analysis using questionnaires.

The purpose of the survey analysis of data with regards to this research study was to make conclusions that are valid so as to lead to good decision (Olannye, 2006). Analysis is the rational processing of data with the use of statistical tools, to produce information. A quantitative approach was vital for this study to achieve a "numerical description of variables, attitudes, or opinions" of a large population base (Creswell, 2009).

Data Collection

Data was collected from 80 employees using a self-report questionnaire. The method of data collection is from both primary data collection and secondary data collection. The questionnaire included measures of employee well-being and job performance in the manufacturing industry.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression analysis.

Presentation of Data, Analyses and Interpretation

This section evaluates acquired data for this study. Data was displayed and interpreted according to questionnaires disbursed to employees in Danade Manufacturing Company, Nigeria. 95 questionnaires were given to the respondents. A total of 80 copies were returned while fifteen (15) were not returned.

Summary of Demographic Respondents

The demographic factors was measured using a demographic questionnaire, which includes questions about age, gender, and tenure. The demographic features of the respondents are presented below:

1. **Age:** Majority of the age of respondents that were between 25-39 years old is 59% and 40-49 year old is 27% while 50-65 years old is 13% as younger employees are required to perform heavy task in the manufacturing company.
2. **Gender:** 62% of the respondents were male employee, and 38% were female employee as more males are required to perform special task in the manufacturing company.

Organizational Wellbeing Practices and Employee Work Behavior in Selected Manufacturing Company, Lagos, Nigeria

3. **Job Tenure:** The respondents who had been working with Danade Manufacturing company shows that 55% are working for (1-10 years); 29% are working for (11-25 years); while 16% are working for (26-35 years).

Summary of Regression Analysis for the Effect of Organizational Wellbeing and Employee Work Behaviour in Danade Manufacturing Company, Lagos State, Nigeria.

Table 4.1

a: Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.6335 ^a	.392	.389	.37678		
a. Predictors: (Constant): Job Performance, Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment						
b: ANOVA						
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	19.277	4	4.764	35.311	.000 ^b
	Residual	28.667	223	.145		
	Total	47.944	227			
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Work Behaviour						
b. Predictors: (Constant)						
c: Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.389	.202		6.120	.000
	Job Performance	.025	.056	.046	0.864	.046
	Job Satisfaction	.284	.021	.349	6.318	.006
	Organizational Commitment	.350	.048	.414	7.454	.004
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Work Behaviour						

R Square value in the regression model of Table 4.1A above provides an indication of the explanatory power of the regression model. R square is simply the percentage of variance in the dependent variable explained by the collection of independent variables. The value of 0.392 means that 39.2% of the variability of employee work behaviour may be explained by the predictor organizational wellbeing variables used in the study. The following part of the output shows the SPSS test of the significance of the correlation coefficient by analysis of variance (ANOVA). The ANOVA table assesses overall significance of the regression model.

The Table 4.1C presents predictor variables coefficients together with p-values. The hypothesis was tested by comparing the decision rule p value of 0.05 with predictor variable p values. The decision rule states that if $p < 0.05$ reject the null for non-significance and conclude that the independent variable is a significant predictor of the dependent variable. The study therefore hypothesized that:

HO1: There is no significant relationship between employee wellbeing and job performance

HO2: There is no significant relationship between employee wellbeing and job satisfaction

HO3: There is no significant relationship between employee wellbeing and organizational commitment

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The results of the test of significance as shown in Table 4.1C specifies that the p-value of job performance is >0.05 ($p = 0.046$). It then rejected the first null hypothesis, H_01 that there is no significant relationship between employee wellbeing and job performance. This can be concluded that the job performance is a significant predictor of the employee work behaviour, as given that the p-value (0.046) is less than the decision p-value $p < 0.05$. The job performance in Danade Manufacturing Company significantly predict the employee work behavior.

The result can be logical for getting a significant relationship between job performance and employee work behavior as against some theories since how employee performs their job is a major factor to determine the organizational wellbeing in Danade Manufacturing Company.

For the second hypothesis; the result of the hypothesis test as shown in the Table 4.1C indicates that the p-value of job satisfaction ($p=0.006$) is less than the decision p-value ($p < 0.05$) hence we reject the second null hypothesis, as stated H_02 , that there is no significant effect between employee wellbeing and job satisfaction. The result for job performance shows ($r = 0.210$; $F= 35.311$; $t = 6.120$; $p < 0.05$). It is therefore concluded from the test that the organizational wellbeing which promotes job satisfaction is a significant predictor of employee work behavior as job satisfaction which derives a key factor to promote good employee work behavior in Danade Manufacturing Company.

For the third hypothesis; the result of the hypothesis test as shown in Table 4.1C indicates that the p-value of the automation for reward practices ($p=0.004$) is less than the decision p-value ($p < 0.05$) hence we reject the second null hypothesis, as stated H_03 , that there is no significant effect between employee wellbeing and organizational commitment. The result for organizational commitment shows ($F= 35.311$; $t = 7.454$; $p < 0.05$). It is therefore concluded from the test for organizational commitment is a significant predictor of employee work behavior in Danade Manufacturing Company.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the effect of organizational wellbeing practices on employee work behavior and performance and also identifies the dimensions of wellbeing practices that are most strongly related to employee work behavior and performance in Danade Manufacturing Company, Lagos. The results shows a significant positive relationship between organizational wellbeing and employee performance and the study concludes that organizational wellbeing is a factor in influencing job behaviour in manufacturing companies.

An organization with effective wellbeing practices positively results to more satisfied employees with good physical, mental, social and economic health which will give rise to a more productive growth in the organization. Employees are motivated to improve their performance and output as a result when organizational wellbeing practices are incorporated into the workplace which will benefits them in the long run.

For Danade Manufacturing company to capture high productivity from their employees, they should avoid subjecting their employees to work conditions that may likely result to physical injuries or stress, frustration, and other mental health risks and should in its place embrace initiatives which include's job flexibility, reward, career progression, workplace safety, work life balance, learning and development opportunities, and other wellbeing practices which will transforms the employee to happy and motivated employees with high dedication, commitment, and satisfaction, thus improving productivity and the organization's general performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Manufacturing organizations should prioritize wellbeing practices by providing a supportive work environment, promoting work life balance, and make provisions for employee wellness programs.
2. The study recommended that manufacturing companies should implement wellbeing practices that will stimulate employee engagement and behaviour, job satisfaction and productivity.
3. Manufacturing organizations should regularly carry out organizational wellbeing surveys to monitor employee wellbeing and regularly identify areas for improvement.

Area for Further Research

The study recommended suggestion for further investigations for future researchers to comport more studies in this topic to ascertain other independent variables that would affect the employee work behaviour.

REFERENCES

- 1) Altomonte, S., Allen, J., Bluysen, P. M., Brager, G., Hescong, L., Loder, A., ... & Wargoeki, P. (2020). Ten questions concerning well-being in the built environment. *Building and Environment*, 180, 106949. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2020.106949>
- 2) Anderson, T. and Kanuka, H., 2006. *E-research*. Boston, MA: Allyn and Bacon.
- 3) Armstrong, M. and Taylor, S., 2014. *Armstrong's handbook of human resource management practice*. 13th ed. London: Kogan page.
- 4) Armstrong, M., 2016. *Armstrong's handbook of management and leadership for HR: developing effective people skills and better leadership and management*. 4 ed. London: Kogan Page.
- 5) Armstrong, M. and Taylor, S., 2020. *Armstrong's handbook of human resource management practice*. 15th ed. London ; New York ; New Delhi: Kogan Page.
- 6) Asare, B., Kwasnicka, D., Powell, D. and Robinson, S., 2021. Health and well-being of rotation workers in the mining, offshore oil and gas, and construction industry: a systematic review. *BMJ Global Health*, 6(7), p.e005112.
- 7) Bach, S. and Edwards, M., 2013. *Managing human resources*. 5th ed. Wiley.
- 8) Bakker, A.B., Hetland, J., Olsen, O.K. and Espevik, R. (2019), "Daily strengths use and employee wellbeing: the moderating role of personality", *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, Vol.92No.1, pp.144-168.
- 9) Christensen, M., 2017. *Healthy Individuals in Healthy Organizations: The Happy Productive Worker Hypothesis. The Positive Side of Occupational Health Psychology*, pp.155-169.
- 10) Creswell, J. (2009) *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 3rd ed. London: SAGE Publications Ltd. <http://www.sagepub.com/repository/binaries/pdfs/HistoryofMethods.pdf>. (Accessed on 4/6/13).
- 11) Holbeche, L., 2009. *Aligning Human Resources and Business Strategy*, 2nd Edition. 2nd ed. Amsterdam, Boston: Butterworth-Heinemann.
- 12) Kun, A. and Gadancz, P., 2019. Workplace happiness, well-being and their relationship with psychological capital: A study of Hungarian Teachers. *Current Psychology*, 41(1), pp.185-199.
- 13) Lowe, G. and Graves, F., 2016. *Redesigning Work: A Blueprint for Canada's Future Wellbeing and Prosperity*. University of Toronto Press.
- 14) Pajic, S., 2022. *Will the Inclusive Dream Make a Happy Team? A Study on how Inclusive Leadership affects Career Sustainability and the Roles of Psychological Safety and Organization-Based Self-Esteem*.
- 15) Olanye, P. A. (2006) *Research Methods for Business: A Skill Building Approach*. Lagos & Asaba; Peejen Publication.
- 16) Shin, D. and Konrad, A.M. (2017), "Causality between high-performance work systems and organizational performance", *Journal of Management*, Vol.43No.4, pp.973-997.
- 17) Wilkins, S., Butt, M. and Annabi, C., 2017. The influence of organisational identification on employee attitudes and behaviours in multinational higher education institutions. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 40(1), pp.48-66.
- 18) Wright, T., Cropanzano, R. and Bonett, D., 2007. The moderating role of employee positive wellbeing on the relation between job satisfaction and job performance. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 12(2), pp.93-104.
- 19) Zhao, T., Li, H., Zheng, L. and Zhang, Y., 2022. How Dispositional Gratitude Shapes Employee Well-being and Organizational Commitment: The Mediating Roles of Leader-Member Exchange and Coworker Exchange. *Journal of Career Assessment*, p.106907272210998.